

Confirmatory data for the PMC9335190

This report describes an Independent Confirmation of one data from the following publication

Yeon-Sook Choi, Myung Ji Kim, Eun A Choi, Sinae Kim, Eun ji Lee, Mi-Ju Kim, Yeon Wook Kim, Jae Yun Jung, Hyori Kim, Kyung Kon Kim, Jin Young Kim, Seung-Mo Hong, Song Cheol Kim and Suhwan Chang (2022), Antibody-Mediated Blockade for Galectin-3 Binding Protein in Tumor Secretome Abrogates PDAC Metastasis, *PNAS*, 119(30):e2119048119

Recently, we found a beta-actin blot of Fig 5G was duplicated from the Fig.6C in another publication [*Oncotarget* 10.18632/oncotarget.4827 (2015)]. Therefore, we decided to repeat the western experiment of Fig 5G to confirm the original result is correct.

The results are shown below.

New result by repeating experiment



Original Fig. 5G in the PNAS article



As shown above, both datasets indicate the treatment of EGFR inhibitor (Erlotinib (Erl) or Gefitinib (Gef)) to a primary pancreatic cancer cell line (110621) inhibits the protein expression of Gal-3BP, along with the reduced phospho-EGFR level.